

Entrepreneurship Education Policies: Global Approaches, National Agendas, and the SDG Nexus

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The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are rapidly emerging as the guiding framework for both global and domestic public policy-making, in Qatar and in other countries.

There are 17 SDGs, and they have been usually considered singly, each on their own as a goal, but it is slowly being realized that their true power and inspiration comes through a nexus of mutually reinforcing goals.

For example, Goal 4 is about education: “Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all.” The challenge becomes greater but more inspiring if we consider Goal 4 alongside Goal 5 (gender equality) and Goal 8 (sustainable and inclusive economic growth). What kind of education would support gender equality and sustainable growth? Or sustainable consumption (Goal 12), combat climate change (Goal 13), or halt biodiversity loss (Goal 15)?

As more governments try to support economic growth by fostering entrepreneurship through education, they are realizing that this has to be education for sustainability and harnessed to a nexus of SDGs, and not just one of them. The targets and indicators for [Goal 4](#) reflect this, and in particular mention (Target 4.4) entrepreneurship as part of a modern educational skill set. As Qatar continues to develop its own national programs to support entrepreneurship, a key question is what lessons (positive and negative) can be drawn from existing models?

Are there any best and worst practices? Are there any patterns to existing programs in either program design or delivery? How well are these programs doing in terms of SDGs?

ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION: INTERNATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS, NATIONAL STRATEGIES

Given the importance of entrepreneurship to innovative economies, governments around the world as well as international development organizations have long supported programs in entrepreneurship education. At the international level, we have selected the following organizations: OECD, World Bank, International Labor Organization, Asian Productivity Organization, European Commission, and the United Nations. Among national governments comparable to Qatar (in size, level of economic development, or as aspirational models because of their reputed success in the field): Singapore, Malaysia, Estonia, Hong Kong, and Brunei.

As more governments try to support economic growth by fostering entrepreneurship through education, they are realizing that this has to be education for sustainability and harnessed to a nexus of SDGs, and not just one of them.

Table 1 presents a synopsis of the international and national entrepreneurship programs, categorized by sponsoring organization, program, target group and focus. Three observations jump out immediately.

First, in terms of target groups, the most favoured are gender (primarily women), and youth. Second, international organizations seem to have a wider range of programming focus, from skills training to “ecosystem support,” to access to financing. National programs are more tightly focused on skills development through education.

By “ecosystem support” we mean programs that are educational in a broader and less specifically institutionally anchored way – ones that aim at developing and supporting risk taking, an entrepreneurial culture, and ease of doing business (through lighter and streamlined regulatory regimes) that signal in some way that entrepreneurship is to be encouraged, admired, and facilitated. The third observation is that almost none of these existing programs place any significant emphasis on SDGs.

The emphasis on gender does pick up on SDG Goal 5, but usually without an explicit reference to it.

As could be expected, UNESCO’s Strategy for Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) (2016-2021) aims to “support the efforts of Member States to enhance the relevance of their TVET systems and to equip all youth and adults with the skills required for employment, decent work, entrepreneurship and lifelong learning, and to contribute to the implementation of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development as a whole” (UNESCO, 2016, p. 6). The Strategy has three priority areas:

1. Fostering youth employment and entrepreneurship
2. Promoting equity and gender equality
3. Facilitating the transition to green economies and sustainable societies

Some domestic country programs (e.g., Hong Kong, Brunei) are incorporating sustainability as a feature of entrepreneurship, but it is “sustainability light”.

Table 1: Synopsis: International and National Entrepreneurship Education Programs

INTERNATIONAL

OECD		
Program	Target Groups/ Sectors	Focus
Entrepreneurship at a Glance	SMEs	Ecosystem Support
Inclusive Entrepreneurship in Europe	Gender, Youth, Migrants, Unemployed	Ecosystem Support
Centre for Entrepreneurship, SMEs, Regions and Cities	SMEs	Ecosystem Support
HEInnovate	Higher Education	Skills, Ecosystem Support

World Bank		
Program	Target Groups/ Sectors	Focus
International Finance Corporation (IFC)	SMEs	Access to Finance
Gender Intelligence for Banks	Gender	Ecosystem Support
Women's Entrepreneurship Training	Gender	Skills
Women Entrepreneurship Opportunity Facility	Gender	Access to Finance
Multilateral Investment Guarantee Agency (MIGA)	All Ages	Ecosystem Support
Women's Entrepreneurship Finance Initiative (We-Fi)	Gender	Access to Finance

UNCTAD		
Program	Target Groups/ Sectors	Focus
Entrepreneurship Policy Hub	Policy Makers	Database
Entrepreneurship Policy Framework and Implementation Guidance	All Ages, Educators	Skills
Empretec - Entrepreneurship Training Workshops	MSMEs, All Ages	Skills

APO		
Program	Target Groups/ Sectors	Focus
Rural Entrepreneurship Development	Rural Entrepreneurs, Low Income	Skills
Business Models for Women Entrepreneurs	Gender	Skills

European Commission		
Program	Target Groups/ Sectors	Focus
Entrepreneurship 2020 Action Plan	Youth	Ecosystem Support
Entrepreneurship Competence Framework (EntreComp)	All Ages	Skills
Entrepreneurship Education - A Road to Success	Youth, Educators	Skills

Program	Target Groups/ Sectors	Focus
United Nations		

Program	Target Groups/ Sectors	Focus
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UNIDO		
Entrepreneurship Curriculum Programme (ECP)	Youth - Secondary	Skills

UNESCO		
Entrepreneurship Curriculum Programme (ECP)	Youth - Secondary	Skills

Program	Target Groups/ Sectors	Focus
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ILO		
Youth Entrepreneurship Programme	Youth	Skills
Know About Business (KAB)	Youth	Skills
Start and Improve Your Business (SIYB)	All Ages	Skills
Gender and Entrepreneurship Together (GET Ahead)	Gender, Low Income	Skills

NATIONAL

Singapore		
Program	Target Groups/ Sectors	Focus
Singapore's 21st Century Competencies (21CC) Framework	Youth; Skills	Skills
Applied Learning Programme in Business and Entrepreneurship	Youth - Secondary	Skills
Young Entrepreneurs Scheme for Schools (YES! Schools)	Youth - Primary & Secondary	Skills
Action Community for Entrepreneurship (ACE)	SME	Ecosystem Support

Malaysia		
Program	Target Groups/ Sectors	Focus
Malaysia's Education Blueprint 2013-2025	Youth	Skills
Strategic Plan on Entrepreneurship Development in Higher Education 2013-2015	Youth - Higher Education	Skills
National Entrepreneurship Framework	Youth, Low Income, Unemployed	Skills; Access to Finance
Professional Training & Education for Growing Entrepreneurs (PROTÉGÉ)	Youth	Skills
National Dual Training System	Unemployed	Skills
I-KIT Programme	Gender, Low Income	Skills

Estonia		
Program	Target Groups/ Sectors	Focus
Estonian Entrepreneurship Growth Strategy 2014-2020	Youth	Skills
Entrepreneurship Education Program (ETTEVÕTLUSÕPPE PROGRAMM)	Youth, Educators	Skills
Youth Entrepreneurship Development Program (ENTRUM)	Youth	Skills

Hong Kong		
Program	Target Groups/ Sectors	Focus
Junior Achievement Hong Kong	Youth - Secondary	Skills
School-Company-Parent Program	Youth - Secondary	Skills
MIT Innovation Academy Teaching Lab	Youth - Secondary, Educators	Skills

Brunei		
Program	Target Groups/ Sectors	Focus
National Entrepreneurship Agenda (NEA)	Youth	Skills
Entrepreneurship Village (EV)	Youth	Skills
Success Weekends	Youth - Primary & Secondary	Skills
Brunei Darussalam Entrepreneurship Education Scheme (BEES)	Youth - Secondary	Skills
LiveWIRE Brunei	All Ages	Skills, Access to Finance
Junior Achievement	Youth - Primary & Secondary	Skills

LESSONS FOR QATAR FROM INTERNATIONAL AND NATIONAL EXPERIENCES

Qatar’s National Vision 2030 and its first (2011-2016) and second (2018-2022) National Development Strategies (NDS) have all highlighted the importance of human capital, economic diversification, private sector development, and ultimately, of entrepreneurship. In NDS-1, three of thirteen targets were designed to strengthen the private sector and promote entrepreneurship. A principal tool was the

Qatar Development Bank, which created a portfolio of services to support companies. NDS-2 highlighted the importance of promoting a vibrant entrepreneurship and innovation culture, especially among Qatari nationals (Ministry of Development Planning and Statistics (Qatar), 2018, p. 99). Specifically, it promised to: “develop programmes to encourage youth scholarships, promote entrepreneurship among Qatari youth.” It also noted the challenges faced by female entrepreneurs, despite progress since NDS-1.

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It is clear that in NDS-2 Qatari policy makers recognize the importance of entrepreneurship, but at the same time they have not specifically flagged entrepreneurship education as a target and tool of policy. More importantly, NDS-2 is fully cognizant of the SDGs and the importance of sustainability – the word is mentioned on 115 of its 337 pages.

A scan of the Qatari entrepreneurship education and support landscape shows a variety of initiatives. The Qatar Foundation, partner universities in Education City, and the Qatar Science and Technology Park (QSTP) are leading examples. In 2020, QSTP will co-host (with the European Innovation Academy) the Arab Innovation Academy. The Qatar Development Bank (QDB) is another primary government policy tool, offering programs in financing, export promotion, business support, and skills and ecosystem development. It co-sponsors the [Qatar Business Incubator](#).

Qatar University has launched a QU Entrepreneurship and Innovation Strategy, both to transform the university and to contribute to the national entrepreneurial ecosystem. Carnegie Mellon University in Qatar (CMU-Q) offers a certificate program ([“Young Entrepreneurs”](#)) for [high school students](#), and the [Bedaya Center for Entrepreneurship and Career Development](#) provides networking and advisory opportunities for Qatari youth. As in the Hong Kong and Brunei examples above, Junior Achievement is also active in Qatar through [Injaz Qatar](#), an NGO that partners with the business community to offer programs (work readiness, financial literacy, entrepreneurship) in elementary, high schools, youth centers and colleges and universities throughout Qatar (see the case study of Injaz in Greene, Brush, Eisenman, Neck, & Perkins, 2015).

The results have been impressive. The 2018 Global Entrepreneurship Index lists Qatar as first in the Arab region and 22nd globally (out of 137 countries) (Ács, Szerb, & Lloyd, 2017).

The 2018/2019 Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (with a sample of 49 countries) presents several positive findings for Qatar (Bosma & Kelley, 2018):

- It was the highest ranked countries in the MENA region for “entrepreneurship context” (consisting of 12 weighted framework conditions), and among the top three for the entire sample (with Indonesia and the Netherlands)
- It was one of only six countries with roughly equal “Total Entrepreneurial Activity” rates for men and women
- For every person starting a business in Qatar, three intend to start one in the next three years
- Among national survey respondents in Qatar, 76.7% give high status to entrepreneurs, and 68.2% consider entrepreneurship as a good career choice (as a comparator, the Republic of Korea’s results were 70% and 52% respectively)

Considering these efforts and these results in Qatar, and comparing them to the review of entrepreneurship education programs, we arrive at one major observation. The international and national cases we summarized above show extensive efforts to embed entrepreneurship in the curriculum across all education levels. However, in Qatar, the emphasis of government policy has been more on economic support, ecosystem policies, and much less on education. Government assistance has “been overseen by an economic rather than an education organization” (Greene et al., 2015, p. 89). The Qatar National Development Strategy does mention entrepreneurial skills and training, but most actual initiatives have been in business support, incubators, science and technology, etc. These are all laudable, but international best practice seems to place equal if not more emphasis on educational efforts in schools. In many countries, these efforts are expressed through a national strategy or an entrepreneurship educational framework overseen by the relevant Ministry of Education.

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This leads us to conclude with one major recommendation, and three additional supporting ones.

Recommendation 1: The Ministry of Education and Higher Education be tasked to develop a strategy to embed entrepreneurship in mid-school through high school. Singapore, Malaysia and Brunei offer useful models. This would involve developing curricular materials as well as teaching training. Injaz Qatar provides a local model of educational-business partnership and SME mentoring that could provide a foundation for a more elaborated program.

Recommendation 2: In addition to delivery of entrepreneurship programs through the school system, Qatar could investigate online self-learning modules and resources. Digital tools have been developed through HEInnovate and the Asian Productivity Organization, and would themselves be innovative delivery channels serving a different clientele than school-age youth.

Recommendation 3: Qatar has an opportunity to develop unique and distinctive programs to support education for social entrepreneurship. Most national and international programs focus on for-profit business, but given Qatar's Islamic heritage and emphasis on charitable service, this could be a type of entrepreneurship education that could both serve the country and provide a model for others.

Recommendation 4: Qatar can be a pioneer on embedding the SDGs into entrepreneurship education. Moreover, it can take an approach that encourages an entrepreneurial, social development oriented emphasis on sustainability. Students could be encouraged to be entrepreneurs developing sustainable products and services that will contribute to the nation's development strategy as well as to its global commitments.

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